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ORGANIZATIONAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF A HEALTHY AND CREATIVE ENVIRONMENT IN THE MANAGERIAL ACTIVITIES OF LEADERS

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ANNOTATION

Young specialists with the above qualities are trusted in the selection of personnel for leadership positions, and special attention is paid to finding capable, talented and talented young people for management activities, regular work with them, training and professional development.

Keywords. *Leader, management activity, leader quality.*

In the process of socio-economic reforms implemented in our country, the development of production, ensuring the economic stability of organizations and enterprises depends to a large extent on the quality of training leaders and specialists who meet the requirements of the time. Today, in the context of building a social economy, the formation of management skills is of special importance in the training of leaders, their qualification improvement and retraining.

Leading personnel play an important role in the effective implementation of public administration. The fate of the democratic changes implemented in the country depends to a large extent on the activities of the people in responsible positions in the state and government agencies, their attitude to work, human qualities and leadership skills. The leader differs from his predecessors in his loyalty to the motherland, dedication, justice, initiative, efficiency, perseverance, inquisitiveness, striving for innovation, demandingness, economic and legal literacy, spiritual maturity, ability to create a healthy and creative environment in the team. Young people with the above qualities and qualities are also selected for leadership positions. Trust is given to specialists, and special attention is paid to finding capable, talented and talented young people in management activities, working with them regularly, training and improving their skills.

Today, great importance is attached to people's living and working conditions, social issues and lifestyle. It is not for nothing that our honorable president called 2022 the year of "Glorification of human dignity and active neighborhood". The labor productivity of each employee, the effectiveness of his work depends more on his satisfaction with his work, his spiritual and cultural level, healthy and creative environment in the team, life and living conditions.

Nowadays, great importance is attached to the psychological factors in the management activities of the leaders. Social psychology lessons are held in training courses for managers and professional development courses. In many enterprises, the position of psychologist is included.

Bernard Shaw said that working in a team is a job; desire for work, and desire - rest, leisure. The normative view of the management system is "man - man", where "man" is meant as an object, and "collective" i.e. team work is distinguished as the subject of the team.

In the process of management, the leader should study each employee under his command, make a psychological diagnosis, have the characteristics of social observation, and be able to determine whether the capabilities of the employees are fully compatible with the work they are doing. One of the most important means of maintaining team cohesion and a healthy moral environment in it is the leader's communicability, i.e. maintaining all-round communication.

The functional task of the leader is primarily determined by the creation of a system of mutual relations in the joint activities of employees.

Qualitative aspects of the leader: adaptability, leadership, coordination of social functions; communication (openness in the relationship, the ability to persuade people, establishing business relations); Qualities such as resistance to stress are among the main characteristics of a leader.

In addition, scientists define 5 qualitative characteristics of a leader in team management in the following order: principledness, fairness, knowledge of the work, competence, demandingness and organizational characteristics.

Respect, reputation - attention is a unit of measure recognized by the society, it is manifested by recognizing and accepting the decisions made by the leader of the team as his own opinion and advice. One of the quality aspects of a leader is to deal with creative ideas put forward by the team, rather than with actions taken using his official position. This indicates the ability of the leader to create a healthy and creative environment in the team when managing educational institutions. Therefore, the leader should have a high level of prestige (respect) in accordance with his position and position.

Leadership is carried out more by influencing the team by being able to direct, convince, and gain confidence in it (democratic style), as well as by forcing through orders (autocratic style).

Success in leadership does not depend on the authority of the leader in terms of his position, but on his reputation - position, energy, extensive experience, extensive knowledge, talent, creation of a creative atmosphere in the team, and his intelligence. The democratic style of leadership, both in the centralized and decentralized management method, leads to an increase in production productivity through a creative approach, first of all, entrepreneurship, by solving entrepreneurial problems in a team way. What to do, how to be a good leader knows what to do, organizes the work correctly, can direct the team towards the goal and achieve an effective result.

Success in leadership activities depends on the leader's and the entire team's interest in work, increasing creativity through a healthy environment in the team, high-level organization, and striving to organize work in order to achieve the goal.

Another important characteristic of a leader is to clearly define the tasks of employees, to give them leadership powers and to achieve good results by managing them wisely.

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